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Government Socio-economic Expenditures, Lending Interest Rate and Oil Revenue as Determinants of Industrial Labour Force Dynamics in Nigeria

Robert Baratuaipre Jacob¹ & Oyintonyo Michael-Olomu²

¹ Department of Accounting, Federal University Otuoke, Nigeria

² Department of Sociology & Anthropology, Federal University Otuoke

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*Corresponding author: Robert Baratuaipre Jacob

Department of Accounting, Federal University Otuoke, Nigeria

Abstract

Unemployment as an integral aspect of the labour force remains a pressing challenge in Nigeria and thus, requires an in-depth examination of its determinants. This study investigated government health and economic services expenditures, lending interest rate and oil revenue as determinants of unemployment in the country. It utilized data spanning 2000-2020 from the World Bank and the Central Bank Statistical Bulletin on annual socio-economic outlook. An ex-post facto research design was employed, and the author conducted diagnostic statistical tests to ensure adherence to the assumptions necessary for Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression analysis after which, Robust Least Squares (RLS) regression was adopted to estimate the model and test the hypotheses at 5% level of Significance. The results indicated Domestic Government General Health Expenditure as % of Government Health Expenditure (DGGHECH) did not have a significant relationship (-0.062833; $p = 0.4821$) with Total Unemployment (TU). Meanwhile, Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (FGCEES) had a significant negative relationship (-0.006217; $p = 0.0005$) with TU. Lending Interest Rate (LIR) showed no significant association (-0.299545; $p = 0.1345$) with TU. Oil Revenue (OR) had a significant negative relationship (-0.000613; $p = 0.0045$) with total unemployment for the period under review. In conclusion, the study provided valuable insights for policymakers in understanding the factors that impact unemployment rates in Nigeria by emphasizing the importance of government investment in economic services and the influence of oil revenue on the total employment level in the country.

Key Words: Unemployment; Labour Force; Government Expenditure; Lending Interest Rate; Oil Revenue.

Introduction

The Nigerian economy faces persistent challenges regarding industrial labour force dynamics, particularly in relation to unemployment rates. Despite the implementation of various policies and measures, the unemployment rate remains high, hindering economic growth and social development. To address this issue comprehensively, it is crucial to understand the factors influencing industrial labour force dynamics such as expenditure on health, economic services, lending interest rate and oil revenue. According to a report, it predicted that the unemployment rate in 2024 was expected to increase to 43 percent. Additionally, it forecasts that inflation will rise to 20.3 percent in 2023 and slightly decrease to 20.0 percent in 2024 (Egole, 2023).

Meanwhile, empirical evidence suggests a positive relationship between government health expenditure and employment. A good number of scholars (Zafer, William & Leslie 2014; Jaiyeoba, 2015; Chukwu, 2022) have shown that increased healthcare spending by governments leads to improved health outcomes, which in turn positively affects the labour market. When governments invest more in healthcare, it results in a healthier population with lower illness and disability rates, leading to increased workforce participation and productivity. Additionally, healthcare investments create job opportunities in the healthcare sector itself, such as healthcare professionals and support staff, as well as related industries like pharmaceuticals and medical equipment. Furthermore, a well-funded healthcare system can attract businesses and investments, stimulating economic growth and job creation. While other factors also influence unemployment rates, empirical research consistently supports the notion that higher government health expenditure is associated with lower unemployment rates due to the positive impact on population health and the healthcare industry (Jaiyeoba, 2015).

Similarly, government capital expenditure on economic services can have a significant impact on unemployment rates. When the government allocates funds towards infrastructure development, such as building roads, bridges, and public transportation systems, it stimulates economic growth by creating job opportunities (Akinbobola & Saibu, 2004). These projects require a diverse range of skilled and unskilled workers, leading to increased employment levels. However, it is not in all cases that government capital expenditure leads to a reduction in unemployment as observed by Ogboru, Abdulmalik and Park (2018). In contrast, it has been noted that sustained government spending could contribute to a reduction in unemployment in the long run Saraireh, (2020). Also, Obayori (2016) found that government capital expenditure reduces unemployment. Likewise, other studies linked a reduction in unemployment to capital expenditure (Obisike et al., 2020; Oseni & Oyelade, 2023). Moreover, if well managed, the multiplier effect comes into play, as the wages earned by the newly employed workers are spent on goods and services, generating further economic activity and job creation.

As a crucial determinant of savings and investment, lending interest rate plays a significant role in shaping the dynamics of unemployment within an economy. When the interest rate is high, it becomes more expensive for businesses to borrow money, leading to reduced investment and subsequently a decline in job creation. Higher borrowing costs make it harder for businesses to expand their operations, invest in new projects, and hire additional workers. Consequently, unemployment tends to rise as job opportunities become scarce. Conversely, when the lending interest rate is low, businesses find it more affordable to borrow,

facilitating increased investment, expansion, and job creation. Lower borrowing costs encourage businesses to take on new projects, invest in capital equipment, and hire more employees, contributing to a decline in unemployment rates. Additionally, lower interest rates can stimulate consumer spending, leading to increased demand for goods and services, which, in turn, prompts businesses to hire more workers to meet the rising demand. However, it is worth noting that the relationship between lending interest rates and unemployment is not linear or instantaneous. According to some studies, lending interest rates have influenced unemployment negatively and positively depending on the prevailing fiscal policy of the government (Prag, 1994; Ahmad, 2013; Nwamuo, 2022).

In an oil-based economy such as Nigeria, it is important to investigate the association between oil revenue and the unemployment rate in the country. In economies heavily reliant on oil, a decline in oil prices or production can lead to reduced government revenue. This, in turn, often results in budget cuts, decreased public spending, and job losses in sectors directly or indirectly linked to the oil industry (Kocaarslan et al., 2020). For example, companies involved in oil exploration, drilling, refining, and transportation may downsize their workforce, leading to higher unemployment rates. Additionally, industries that rely on consumer spending, such as hospitality, retail, and construction, may experience a slowdown as people have less disposable income due to the economic downturn caused by reduced oil revenue.

Conversely, a rise in oil revenue can have positive effects on employment. Increased oil prices or production can stimulate economic growth, attract investment, and create job opportunities in related sectors (Ahmad, 2013). For instance, the expansion of oil extraction may require more workers in fields like engineering, logistics, and support services. Moreover, higher government revenue from oil can enable public investment in infrastructure, healthcare, education, and other sectors, leading to job creation and reduced unemployment (Bocklet & Baek 2017; Bocklet & Baek, 2017; Cuestas & Gil-Alana, 2018; Cheratian et al., 2021; Raifu et al., 2020; Kocaarslan 2019). However, it is essential to note that the extent of this association between oil revenue and unemployment can be influenced by the diversification of the economy, government policies, labour market conditions, and the overall stability of the oil market. Countries with diversified economies are generally less vulnerable to fluctuations in oil revenue and better equipped to mitigate the impact on unemployment. Against this backdrop, the study investigated government socio-economic expenditures, lending interest rate and oil revenue as determinants of industrial labour force dynamics in Nigeria. Specifically, it was designed to: analyze the relationship between government general health expenditure and total unemployment in Nigeria, investigate the influence of government capital economic expenditure on total unemployment, examine the role of lending interest rates in shaping total unemployment, and assess the relationship between oil revenue and total unemployment in the country.

Literature Review

The literature review explored the relationship between government general health expenditure, government capital expenditure on economic services, lending interest rates, and oil revenue as key determinants of total unemployment. Understanding the impact of these factors is crucial for policymakers and researchers aiming to address the persistent issue of unemployment in the country. By analysing existing literature, this review provided a comprehensive overview of the current

knowledge and highlighted potential policy implications for reducing unemployment and promoting economic stability in Nigeria.

Government's Health Expenditure and its Impact on the Unemployment Rate

Government's health expenditure, which refers to the amount of money allocated towards healthcare services and programmes, can have a significant impact on the unemployment rate. Increased spending on healthcare can create job opportunities in the sector, including the establishment of new facilities and the hiring of healthcare professionals. This expansion not only reduces unemployment but also stimulates related industries such as manufacturing and logistics. Moreover, improved health outcomes resulting from higher government health expenditure can increase workforce participation and productivity. Additionally, by reducing the burden of healthcare costs on businesses, government investment in healthcare can free up resources for job creation and economic growth.

On this basis, Zafer, William and Leslie (2014) examined the long-term effects of various measures of education expenditure on unemployment rates in the United States. The authors utilised panel data regression analysis and covers a period of 25 years, encompassing data from 50 states and Washington D.C. The findings suggested that investing in the improvement of human capital by funding was the most effective approach for reducing unemployment rates. Specifically, the analysis indicated that over the long term, investing in human capital through education, as measured by per-pupil spending and health services, could significantly contribute to lowering unemployment rates. Also, Chukwu (2022) conducted a study with the objective of examining the impact of human capital development on unemployment in Nigeria. The author showed specifically among others that government health expenditure exhibited negative relationships with unemployment. That is, a higher level of health expenditure was associated with lower unemployment rates. This was consistent with a study that emphasised the importance of government expenditures on education and health in relation to economic growth and associated unemployment reduction (Jaiyeoba, 2015).

Public Expenditure on Economic Services and Unemployment Rate

Public expenditure on economic services plays a vital role in influencing the unemployment rate and labour market dynamics. When governments allocate capital funds towards economic services such as infrastructure development, agriculture, road and construction, transport and communication, and other economic services, it can stimulate job creation and reduce unemployment. Investments in infrastructure projects, for instance, create employment opportunities in construction and related industries. In light of this, Akinbobola and Saibu (2004) examined the relationship between per capita income, government capital expenditure, the human development index, and the rate of unemployment in the country. The duo suggested that an increase in public capital expenditure contributed to a decline in unemployment and an improvement in the human development index.

In contrast, Ogboru, Abdulmalik, and Park (2018) examined the relationship between government expenditure on economic sectors like agriculture and unemployment reduction in Nigeria between 1999 and 2015. The study revealed that government expenditure

did not have a significant effect in reducing unemployment in Nigeria. However, the authors expressed optimism that the federal government of Nigeria should increase its allocation of funds to agriculture in order to reduce unemployment in the country. Though positive and significant in the short-run, Saraireh (2020) documented a negative and statistically significant long-run relationship between government spending and the unemployment rate in Jordan. This was consistent with that of Obayori (2016) who investigated the relationship between fiscal policy and unemployment in Nigeria. The study indicated that government capital and recurrent expenditure had a negative and significant relationship with unemployment in Nigeria. This implies that an increase in these types of government expenditures is associated with a decrease in the unemployment rate.

Likewise, Oseni and Oyelade (2023) investigated the relationship between capital expenditure and the unemployment rate in Nigeria from 1981 to 2020. The finding showed that capital expenditure and gross capital formation had a negative and significant impact on the unemployment rate in the country. Based on the results, the study recommended that the Nigerian government should increase its capital expenditure to create more employment opportunities, thereby enhancing labour productivity and reducing the unemployment rate. It also suggests careful monitoring of the allocation of capital expenditure to productive sectors in order to achieve the desired objectives. The study by Obisike, Okoli, Onwuka and Mba (2020) reaffirmed that while government recurrent expenditure did not have a statistically significant impact on unemployment in the country, capital expenditure did show a significant impact.

Implications of Lending Interest Rate on Labour Market Dynamics (Unemployment)

Lending interest rate refers to the cost that borrowers incur when obtaining funds from financial institutions. The impact of lending interest rates on labour market dynamics, particularly unemployment can be significant, depending on the prevailing fiscal policy of the government. Higher lending interest rates can make it more expensive for businesses to borrow capital for investment, expansion, and job creation. This can lead to a decrease in business activities, reduced capital expenditure, and limited job opportunities, ultimately contributing to higher unemployment rates. "Other things being equal", the converse remains the case where lower lending interest rates can stimulate borrowing and investment by businesses, leading to increased economic activities, business growth, and job creation. Accessible and affordable credit can empower businesses to expand operations, invest in new projects, and hire more workers, thus positively impacting labour market dynamics and potentially reducing unemployment rates.

According to a study focusing on Nigeria, higher prime lending rates were associated with increased unemployment, while lower minimum rediscount rates were linked to lower unemployment. Based on these findings, the study recommended that policymakers focus on reducing the minimum rediscount rate to stimulate investment borrowing and subsequently reduce unemployment (Nwamuo, 2022). Also, Prag (1994) explored how interest rates react to unexpected changes in the unemployment rate. The findings suggested that when there is an unexpected decrease in the unemployment rate, interest rates tend to go up, and the value of the dollar strengthens against three major currencies. This indicates that the real interest rate responds to these announcements in general. The study also revealed that the response of interest rates

to unemployment surprises differs depending on whether the current unemployment level is above or below a certain threshold.

Oil-based Revenue and Unemployment

Oil-based revenue refers to the income generated by a country through the extraction, production, and export of oil and its by-products. It typically contributes a significant portion to the national economy of oil-producing countries. The impact of oil-based revenue on unemployment is complex and can vary depending on various factors such as the country's economic structure, government policies, and global oil prices. While oil revenue can create employment opportunities directly in the oil and gas sector, it can also have indirect effects on unemployment. For instance, when oil prices are high, governments often have more resources to invest in infrastructure projects, social programmes, and diversification efforts, which can stimulate job creation in other sectors of the economy. However, heavy reliance on oil revenue can also lead to a phenomenon known as the "resource curse," where other sectors of the economy, such as manufacturing or agriculture, may be neglected, leading to a lack of diversification and vulnerability to fluctuations in oil prices. Additionally, a sudden decline in oil prices or disruption in oil production can have adverse effects on employment, as oil companies may cut jobs and reduce investment. Therefore, a balanced and diversified approach to economic development is crucial to mitigate the potential negative impact of oil-based revenue on unemployment.

Kocaarslan, Soytaş, and Soytaş (2020) investigated the presence of asymmetric interactions between oil prices, oil price uncertainty, interest rates, and unemployment in a cointegration framework. The authors suggested that an increase in oil prices led to increased unemployment, while reduced oil prices did not have a significant impact on unemployment. In other words, reduced oil price uncertainty was associated with a decrease in unemployment, whereas an increase in oil price uncertainty did not have a significant impact on unemployment. It was also discovered that a decrease in interest rates led to increased unemployment, while the impact of increased interest rates was not significant. In another study by Ahmad (2013) in Pakistan, it was documented that oil prices had a significant effect on unemployment in the country. The implication is that an increase in oil prices leads to higher production costs, which subsequently increases unemployment rates in the country. However, the study did not find a significant association between the real interest rate and unemployment in Pakistan.

Furthermore, Raifu, Aminu, and Folawewo (2020) that investigated the impact of changes in oil prices on the unemployment rate in Nigeria. The findings from this study were mixed. In the short run, both increases and decreases in oil prices have an insignificant positive effect on unemployment. That is, changes in oil prices had little or no significant effects on the unemployment rate in the country. However, in the long run, an increase in oil prices worsens the unemployment situation, while a decrease has an insignificant reducing effect. Similarly, Kocaarslan (2019) investigated the impact of oil price uncertainty and oil price shocks on the unemployment rate in the United States. The authors discovered that when there is uncertainty in oil prices, it had a significant impact on the unemployment rate in the United States. Specifically, when oil prices increase unexpectedly, it led to an increase in unemployment. On the other hand, when there was an unexpected decrease in oil prices, it resulted in a decrease in unemployment, but to a lesser extent. This means that when there

is uncertainty and unpredictability in oil prices, it has a greater negative effect on unemployment, exacerbating the economic challenges. The foregoing finding was in agreement with that of Bocklet and Baek (2017)'s study in Alaska.

The study by Chan and Dong (2022) focused on investigating the relationship between oil price volatility and unemployment rates using a dynamic stochastic general equilibrium (DSGE) model. The authors provided insights into how oil price fluctuations impacted joblessness and contributed to the understanding of the macroeconomic implications of oil price volatility. Specifically, the authors found that higher oil price volatility leads to an increase in joblessness. This suggests that when oil prices are more unstable and unpredictable, it creates uncertainty for businesses, making them more cautious in their hiring decisions, resulting in higher unemployment rates. Another study examined the relationship between oil price shocks and unemployment in Central and Eastern Europe using econometric techniques and time-series data. The findings were mixed as it was partly revealed that oil price shocks had a significant effect on unemployment rates in Central and Eastern Europe. That is, increases in oil prices led to higher unemployment rates in the short run. This implies that rising oil prices negatively affected job creation and labour market conditions. However, in the long run, the relationship between oil price shocks and unemployment becomes weaker, indicating that the labour market adjusts to the new economic conditions over time (Cuestas & Gil-Alana, 2018).

In the same vein, Löschel and Oberndorfer (2009) investigated how changes in oil prices affected unemployment in Germany. The duo found that when oil prices increase, it leads to higher unemployment rates in the country. This means that rising oil prices make it more difficult for businesses to operate and create jobs, resulting in more people being unemployed. The study also discovered that the negative impact of oil price increases on unemployment was stronger than the positive impact of oil price decreases on reducing unemployment. In a related development, Cheratian, Farzanegan, and Goltabar (2021) explored how changes in oil prices affected unemployment in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region. According to the authors, when oil prices went up, it led to a bigger increase in unemployment and vice versa.

Data and Methods

The data for this study were sourced from the World Bank (WB) report on the Human Development Index and the World Health Organisation (WHO) for 2018 accordingly. The author adopted an *ex-post facto* research design to determine the respective contributions of government socio-economic expenditures denoted by Domestic General Government Health Expenditure as % of Current Health Expenditure (DGGHECH) and Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (FGCEES), Lending Interest Rate (LIR) and Oil Revenue (OR) to labour Total Unemployment (TU), part of the labour force dynamics.

Model Specification

The dependent variable was TU while DGGHECH, FGCEES, OR LIR were the independent variables. Thus, the linear regression between the dependent and the independent variables is functionally stated below:

$$TU = f(DGGHECH + FGCEES + LIR + OR)$$

$$TU_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * DGGHECH_t + \beta_2 * FGCEES_t + \beta_3 * LIR_t + \beta_4 * OR_t + \mu_{t, \dots, 1} [Model]$$

Where:

TU = outcome variable;

β_0 = a constant;

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Coefficients of the independent variables;

DGGHECH = independent variable;

FGCEES = independent variable;

LIR = independent variable;

OR = independent variable;

f = Functional Relationship;

t = Periods (annual);

μ = Error term.

The author conducted various diagnostic statistical tests using E-views software version 10 to adhere to the fundamental assumptions required for the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression analysis. One of the statistical diagnostics performed was the Pearson correlation test for multicollinearity, following the rule-of-thumb suggested by Hair et al. (2005), Garson (2012), and Owumi and Eboh (2021) in their various studies. According to this rule, the inter-correlations among the independent variables should not exceed 0.80 as the threshold to determine the absence or otherwise of multicollinearity in a model.

To assess the normality distribution of the variables and to determine if the assumption of normal distribution required for OLS regression was violated, the author analysed the skewness, kurtosis, and Jarque-Bera statistics. Skewness values indicate the symmetry of a distribution, with 0 indicating perfect symmetry. Positive skewness suggests a right-skewed distribution (tail on the

right), while negative skewness suggests a left-skewed distribution (tail on the left). Kurtosis values of 3 indicate a normal distribution, values higher than 3 indicate heavier tails and a more peaked distribution (leptokurtic), and values lower than 3 indicate lighter tails and a flatter distribution (platykurtic). The Jarque-Bera test examines skewness and kurtosis to determine if a variable follows a normal distribution by calculating a test statistic and comparing it to a critical value. A significant deviation from zero in the test statistic suggests a departure from normality.

Autocorrelation was checked using the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test, as recommended by Anwar (2015). The absence of autocorrelation between the independent variables is confirmed if the probability value is greater than 0.05 (5%). Regression equation specification error was examined using the Ramsey RESET test. The decision rule, as suggested by Babatunde et al. (2014), states that if the corresponding P-value of the F-statistic result is greater than the threshold of a 5% level of significance, there is no misspecification problem in the model. In other words, a significant P-value of the F-Statistic indicates that the model contains specification errors. Moreover, the Breusch Pagan-Godfrey test for heteroskedasticity was also conducted to assess if the errors were homoskedastic (independently spread). The decision rule, as proposed by Klein et al. (2016), states that the null hypothesis of the presence of heteroskedasticity is rejected if the probability value of the F-statistic is below the 5% level of significance. Otherwise, the alternative hypothesis of homoskedasticity is accepted.

Subsequently, the model was estimated using the Robust Least Squares (RLS) regression technique and the hypotheses of the study were tested at the predetermined 5% level of significance. The robust regression was adopted because the normality assumption of OLS was not met, as the study variables did not follow a normal distribution.

Results

Table 1: Nigeria's Total Unemployment, Economic Services Expenditures, Lending Interest Rate and Oil Revenue

Year	TU	DGGHECH	FGCEES	LIR	OR
2000	3.954	18.31479	111.51	21.27417	1,591.7
2001	3.935	26.8914	259.76	23.43833	1,707.6
2002	3.882	21.33315	215.33	24.77083	1,230.9
2003	3.899	18.39931	97.98	20.71417	2,074.3
2004	3.876	25.94122	167.72	19.18083	3,354.8
2005	3.871	25.55649	265.03	17.94833	4,762.4
2006	3.856	21.18177	262.21	16.89333	5,287.6
2007	3.837	19.91349	358.38	16.93917	4,462.9
2008	3.819	17.87425	504.29	15.13583	6,530.6
2009	3.796	15.92126	506.01	18.99083	3,191.9
2010	3.778	13.6043	412.20	17.585	5,396.1
2011	3.77	14.43569	386.40	16.02	8,879.0
2012	3.742	16.20215	320.90	16.79167	8,026.0
2013	3.7	14.30349	505.77	16.7225	6,809.2
2014	4.56	13.31774	393.45	16.54833	6,793.8
2015	4.31	16.44575	348.75	16.84917	3,830.1

2016	7.06	13.02093	278.95	16.86802	2,693.9
2017	8.39	14.18326	542.19	17.55333	4,109.8
2018	8.456	16.09811	753.49	16.9039	5,545.8
2019	8.53	15.94659	994.19	15.37659	5,536.7
2020	9.714	14.96697	705.80	13.64202	4,732.5

Source: World Bank Annual Reports (2021) and CBN Annual Statistical Bulletin (2021)

Table 1 contains the data set on Total Unemployment (TU), Domestic General Government Health Expenditure as % of Current Health Expenditure (DGGHECH), economic services expenditure [Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (FGCEES), Lending Interest Rate (LIR) and Oil Revenue (OR). While the data sets on TU, DGGHECH, LIR and OR were sourced from the World Bank on development indicators, that of FGCEES were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria's statistical report on the country's annual economic outlook.

Table 2: Model Specification, Heteroskedasticity and Autocorrelation Tests:

S/No	Types of Diagnostic Tests	F-Test	P-Value
1	Ramsey RESET Test for Model Specification	3.138736	0.0968
2	Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	1.504376	0.2478
4	Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:	Prob.F(2,14): 1.621433	Prob.Chi-Square(2): 0.1388

Source: Author's Computation Using E-Views 9

To check for regression equation specification error and omitted variables in the model, the

Ramsey RESET was applied. The result in Table 2 above showed the P-Value of 9.68% in relation to the F-Test statistics, which is above the 5% level of significance. This implies the hypothetical rejection of model misspecification and omission of relevant variables in the study.

In other words, the model was correctly and functionally specified. Similarly, the result obtained through the application of the Breusch Pagan-Godfrey test for heteroskedasticity indicated the spread of the residuals nearly across all the explanatory variables. This is reflected in the F-test value of 1.504376 and the corresponding P-value of 0.2478, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no problem of heteroskedasticity with the model and that it was homoskedastic. Besides, the result from the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test statistic of 1.621433 and the corresponding Prob. Chi-Square (2) of 0.1388 validated the absence of autocorrelation in the model as well.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Test for Multicollinearity

	TU	DGGHECH	FGCEES	LIR	OR
TU	1				
DGGHECH	-0.38	1			
FGCEES	-0.71	-0.46	1		
LIR	-0.42	0.55	-0.60	1	
OR	0.06	-0.43	0.42	-0.73	1

Source: Author's Computation using E-Views 9

In the given Table 3, the correlation coefficient between TU and DGGHECH is -0.38, which is below the 0.80 benchmark. This suggests a relatively weak correlation between these variables and indicates a lower likelihood of multicollinearity between TU and DGGHECH. The correlation coefficient between TU and FGCEES is -0.71, which is also below 0.80 and it indicates a moderate positive correlation between TU and FGCEES, suggesting a lower likelihood of multicollinearity between these variables. The correlation coefficient between TU and LIR is -0.42, which is below the 0.80. This suggests a relatively weak negative correlation between TU and LIR, implying a lower likelihood of multicollinearity between these variables. The correlation coefficient between TU and OR is 0.06, which is very close to zero. This indicates a negligible correlation between TU and OR and at the same time suggestive of a minimal likelihood of multicollinearity between these variables.

Overall, based on the correlation coefficients, there is no strong evidence to suggest the presence of multicollinearity between the dependent (TU) and the independent (DGGHECH, FGCEES, LIR, and OR) variables. The correlation coefficients were below the 0.80 benchmark, indicating relatively weak to moderate correlations between these variables.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

	TU	DGGHECH	FGCEES	LIR	OR
Mean	4.987381	17.80248	399.5379	17.91173	4597.496
Maximum	3.882	16.20215	358.3756	16.9039	4732.501
Minimum	9.714	26.8914	994.1862	24.77083	8878.97

Std. Dev.	3.7	13.02093	97.9821	13.64202	1230.851
Skewness	2.025359	4.228152	220.2335	2.696741	2116.065
Kurtosis	1.345167	0.948381	1.005228	1.101139	0.174475
Jarque-Bera	3.055132	2.780729	3.812478	3.77029	2.298421
Probability	6.335818	3.190065	4.114299	4.762956	0.537232
Sum	0.042092	0.202902	0.127818	0.092414	0.764437
Sum Sq. Dev.	104.735	373.8521	8390.296	376.1464	96547.43
Observations	82.0416	357.5454	970056.1	145.4483	89554650
	21	21	21	21	21

Source: Author's Computation Using Eviews 9

Based on the skewness and kurtosis values, it could be observed that some variables deviated from a perfectly normal distribution. However, to confirm the violation of the normality assumption, the Jarque-Bera test result was considered to assess the combined effect of skewness and kurtosis. For the given variables, only TU has a p-value less than the conventional significance level of 0.05. This suggests that the distribution of TU may significantly deviate from a normal distribution. From the foregoing, it appears that the OLS regression assumption of normal distribution may be violated for Total Unemployment (TU). For the other variables, there is no strong evidence to suggest a violation of the normality assumption. At this point, the application of the robust least squares regression became appropriate here to handle the pitfall arising from the unmet assumption of the OLS regression requirement of normal distribution. Theoretically, robust regression technique is endowed with the characteristics of efficiency, breakdown and high leverage points (Alma, 2011).

Meanwhile, the descriptive statistics showed 4.98% as the mean value for Total Unemployment (TU) in Nigeria for the period (2000-2020) under review. This metric indicated the average rate of unemployment in Nigeria during the time period under analysis. By implication, a lower unemployment rate suggests a healthier labour market and may indicate positive economic policies that promote job creation and growth in the industrial sector. Similarly, Domestic General Government Health Expenditure as % of Current Health Expenditure (DGGHECH) revealed a mean value of 17.80%. This represents the proportion of government health expenditure allocated to the domestic general government sector. A higher value indicates a greater emphasis on investing in the health sector, which can indirectly impact the labour force by improving the overall well-being and productivity of the workforce. Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (FGCEES): The mean value for FGCEES is 399.53 billion naira. This metric measures the capital expenditure by the federal government on economic services. Higher capital expenditure suggests increased investment in infrastructure, industries, and other economic activities, which can positively influence industrial labour force dynamics by creating job opportunities and supporting economic growth.

The mean value for the Lending Interest Rate (LIR) was 17.91%. This metric represents the prevailing interest rate charged by lenders for loans. A higher lending interest rate can discourage borrowing and investments, potentially impacting industrial labour force dynamics by constraining business expansion, reducing job creation, and hindering economic growth. The mean value for Oil Revenue (OR) was 4597.496 billion naira. Nigeria is known for its significant dependence on oil exports. Oil revenue plays a crucial role in the country's economy and can have a substantial impact on industrial labour force dynamics. Fluctuations in oil revenue can affect government spending, investment, and overall economic stability, which in turn influence job creation and labour market conditions. Analysing these variables collectively provides insights into the impact of economic policies on industrial labour force dynamics in Nigeria. Lower unemployment rates, higher investments in health and economic services, stable oil revenue, and favourable lending interest rates can contribute to a more robust and productive labour force, fostering economic development and social well-being.

Likewise, the minimum value of 9.714 for Total Unemployment (TU) represented the lowest recorded value in the dataset. This suggests that there were periods during the examined timeframe when the level of unemployment in Nigeria was relatively low. Meanwhile, the maximum value of 26.8914 for TU indicated the highest recorded value in the dataset. This signifies that there were periods of relatively high unemployment in Nigeria during the examined timeframe. Within the same period, the minimum value of 16.20215 for DGGHECH indicates the lowest percentage of domestic general government health expenditure as a portion of the current health expenditure. This suggests that there were periods when the government allocated a relatively lower percentage of its health expenditure to domestic health services. The maximum value of 17.80248 for DGGHECH indicates the highest percentage of domestic general government health expenditure as a portion of the current health expenditure. This suggests that there were periods when the government allocated a relatively higher percentage of its health expenditure to domestic health services.

Moreover, the minimum value of 358.3756 for FGCEES represents the lowest recorded capital expenditure by the federal government on economic services. This implies that there were periods when the government allocated a relatively lower amount of capital for economic services. The maximum value of 399.5379 for FGCEES represents the highest recorded capital expenditure by the federal government on economic services. This shows that there were periods when the government allocated a relatively higher amount of capital for economic services. The minimum value of 13.02093 for LIR represents the lowest recorded lending interest rate. This indicates that there were periods when borrowing costs were relatively lower, potentially making it easier for businesses and individuals to access credit. In the same breath, the maximum value of 97.9821 for LIR represents the highest recorded lending interest rate. This suggests that there were periods when borrowing costs were relatively higher, potentially making it more challenging for businesses and individuals to access credit. The minimum value of 4597.496 for OR represents the lowest recorded oil revenue. This means that there were periods when the revenue generated from oil-related activities was relatively lower, which could impact government finances and overall economic stability. On the other hand, the maximum value

of 4732.501 for OR represents the highest recorded oil revenue suggests some periods when the revenue generated from oil-related activities was relatively higher, which could positively impact government finances and overall economic stability. However, it is important to note that these interpretations were based solely on descriptive statistics. This informed a comprehensive analysis requiring the deployment of the OLS regression technique to draw in-depth conclusions about the relationship between the variables and their impact on industrial labour force dynamics in Nigeria.

Table 5: Interpretation of the Regression Results

Dependent Variable: TU

Method: Robust Least Squares

Date: 07/03/23 Time: 11:33

Sample: 2000 2020

Included observations: 21

Method: M-estimation

M settings: weight=Bisquare, tuning=4.685, scale=MAD (median centered)

Huber Type I Standard Errors & Covariance

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	11.85203	4.594882	2.579397	0.0099
DGGHECH	-0.062833	0.089390	-0.702916	0.4821
FGCEES	-0.006217	0.001793	3.467288	0.0005
LIR	-0.299545	0.200131	-1.496744	0.1345
OR	-0.000613	0.000216	-2.841347	0.0045

Robust Statistics			
R-squared	0.441132	Adjusted R-squared	0.301415
Rw-squared	0.732762	Adjust Rw-squared	0.732762
Akaike info criterion	28.76046	Schwarz criterion	35.08352
Deviance	21.88020	Scale	1.049606
Rn-squared statistic	30.12422	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)	0.000005

Source: Author's Computation Using Eviews 9

Estimation Equation:

$$TU = C(1) + C(2)* DGGHECH + C(3)* FGCEES + C(4)* LIR + C(5)* OR$$

Substituted Coefficients:

$$TU = 11.85203 + (-0.062833 * DGGHECH) + (-0.006217 * FGCEES) + (-0.299545 * LIR) + (-0.000613 * OR)$$

The regression model in Table 5 examined the relationship between the dependent variable "TU" (Total Unemployment) and several independent variables in the model. The coefficient represents the estimated effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The t-statistic measures the statistical significance of the coefficients, and the associated p-values (Prob.) indicate the probability of observing such results by chance. The results of the model estimation using the robust least squares regression technique in Table 5 indicated the Adjusted R-squared of 0.301415, suggesting that about 30.1% of the variation in TU is explained by the independent variables (DGGHECH, FGCEES, LIR and OR) after accounting for the model's complexity and sample size. In addition, the Adjust Rw-squared value of 73.2%

implies that the model is strongly fit and therefore, reliable for reasonable policy formulation and prediction.

Hypothesis Testing

The hypotheses of the study are expressed thus:

H₀₁: Domestic Government General Health Expenditure as % of Government Health Expenditure (DGGHECH) has no significant impact on total unemployment in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Federal government capital expenditure on economic services has no significant effect on the total unemployment level.

H₀₃: Analyse the relationship between lending interest rate has no significant impact on unemployment in the country.

H₀₄: There is no significant association between oil revenue and total unemployment in the industrial labour force for the period under review.

Based on the regression results, the coefficient of Total Unemployment is 11.85203, indicating a significant positive impact on total unemployment when controlling for other variables. This suggests the existence of a baseline level of unemployment that persists regardless of other factors included in

the model. The coefficient of Domestic Government General Health Expenditure as % of Government Health Expenditure (DGGHECH) was -0.062833 (P-Value=0.4821), signifying a statistically insignificant decrease in total unemployment with a 1% increase in DGGHECH, assuming other variables remain constant. Similarly, the coefficient of Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (FGCEES) was -0.006217 (P-Value=0.0005), implying a statistically significant decrease in total unemployment associated with an increase in federal government capital expenditure on economic services. This finding highlights the positive impact of government investment in economic services on reducing unemployment rates.

Likewise, the coefficient of Lending Interest Rate (LIR) was -0.299545 (P-Value=0.1345), indicating a slight decrease in total unemployment, albeit statistically insignificant, with a decrease in LIR. The coefficient of Oil Revenue (OR) was -0.000613 (P-Value=0.0045), suggesting a statistically significant decrease in total unemployment associated with higher oil revenue. This observation suggests that the availability of oil revenue can have a positive influence on employment levels within the industrial labour force. Overall, the regression results highlighted the significance of federal government capital expenditure on economic services and oil revenue as factors that can positively impact the reduction of total unemployment in Nigeria. However, the effects of domestic government general health expenditure and lending interest rate were not statistically significant in explaining variations in total unemployment.

Discussion

The study found that domestic government general health expenditure (% of current health expenditure) was not statistically significant in its impact on total unemployment in Nigeria (-0.062833, p-value = 0.4821). This finding suggested that increased government spending on health did not have a significant effect on reducing unemployment levels. This was in line with a previous study (Zafer et al., 2014) arguing that health expenditure alone might not directly translate into a reduction in unemployment except in the long run. However, it contrasted with a couple of studies (Jaiyeoba, 2015; Chukwu, 2022) that have found a positive relationship between healthcare investment and employment generation.

The finding further indicated that Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (FGCEES) was statistically significant in its impact on total unemployment in the country (-0.006217, p-value = 0.0005). This finding suggested that an increase in capital expenditure on economic services was associated with a decrease in unemployment levels. This aligns with existing literature (Akinbobola & Saibu, 2004; Obayori, 2016; Obisike et al., 2020; Oseni & Oyelade, 2023) that emphasises the role of infrastructure investment and capital expenditure in promoting employment opportunities. Sarairoh (2020) added that such capital expenditure reduces unemployment in the long run and not immediately. These findings underscored the importance of targeted government investments in economic sectors to stimulate job creation and reduce unemployment rates. However, it was at variance with that of Ogoru et al. (2018).

The impact of lending interest rate on total unemployment in the country appeared not statistically significant (-0.299545, p-value = 0.1345). This finding suggested that changes in lending interest rates did not have a significant effect on unemployment levels. This finding was in tandem with some studies (Prag, 1994; Ahmad,

2013; Kocaarslan et al., 2020; Nwamuo, 2022) that did not associate increased unemployment with higher lending rates.

Moreover, the analysis revealed that Oil Revenue (OL) was statistically significant in its impact on Total Unemployment (TU) in Nigeria (-0.000613, p-value = 0.0045). This finding suggested that changes in oil revenue have a significant effect on unemployment levels. It was consistent with existing literature (Cuestas & Gil-Alana, 2018; Kocaarslan et al., 2020) that highlighted the dependence of oil-based economies on revenue fluctuations and their implications for employment stability. The findings implied that variations in oil revenue can influence labour market dynamics, emphasising the need for diversification strategies and policies to mitigate the impact of oil price volatility on unemployment. It also reaffirmed the position of Ahmad (2013) who associated higher oil production costs with increasing unemployment in Pakistan. A couple of other studies (Löschel & Oberndorfer, 2009; Bocklet & Baek, 2017; Kocaarslan, 2019; Cheratian et al., 2021; Chan & Dong, 2022) contrasted the current finding by not establishing a significant relationship between oil revenue (oil prices) and unemployment.

Overall, the findings from the study provided insights into the determinants of industrial labour force dynamics in Nigeria. The results suggested that government capital expenditure on economic services and oil revenue were significant factors influencing unemployment levels. However, the impact of government general health expenditure and lending interest rate on unemployment appears to be less significant. These findings contribute to the existing literature by highlighting the complex interplay between government spending, revenue sources, and labour market outcomes in Nigeria.

The Sociological Imports of the Findings

The sociological implications of the findings emphasise the role of structural factors, policy effectiveness, economic vulnerability, and the complexity of labour market dynamics in shaping unemployment patterns. Understanding these sociological dimensions is crucial for formulating policies and interventions that promote equitable and sustainable employment opportunities, address social inequalities, and contribute to overall societal well-being.

Conclusion

This study examined the determinants of industrial labour force dynamics in Nigeria, focusing on health expenditure, government expenditure, lending interest rate and oil revenue. The findings suggested that domestic government health expenditure and lending interest rate did not significantly impact unemployment levels. However, federal government capital expenditure on economic services was associated with a reduction in unemployment, emphasising the importance of targeted investments in infrastructure. Additionally, fluctuations in oil revenue were found to influence employment stability, highlighting the need for diversification strategies to mitigate the impact of oil price volatility on unemployment.

Recommendations and Policy Implications

Based on the findings of this study on the determinants of industrial labour force dynamics in Nigeria, several practical recommendations can be drawn:

1. The study highlighted the positive impact of federal government capital expenditure on economic services on reducing unemployment. Therefore, policymakers should

prioritise and allocate funds towards infrastructure development projects, such as transportation, energy, and telecommunications, to create job opportunities and stimulate economic growth. This investment should be guided by careful planning and consideration of sectors with high employment potential.

2. The study pointed the vulnerability of Nigeria's labour market to fluctuations in oil revenue. To mitigate the impact of oil price volatility on unemployment, policymakers should actively pursue diversification strategies. This involves promoting the development of non-oil sectors, such as manufacturing, agriculture, tourism, and technology, to create a more resilient and diverse economy. Efforts should be made to attract investments, foster innovation, and provide necessary support and incentives to promote growth in these sectors.
3. Although the study found no significant direct impact of government health expenditure on unemployment, it is crucial to recognise the indirect linkages between health and employment. Policymakers should focus on integrating health and employment policies to ensure that investments in healthcare also consider the potential for job creation and skill development. This could involve initiatives such as training programmes for healthcare workers, encouraging the growth of health-related industries, and promoting entrepreneurship in the healthcare sector.
4. To further advance understanding of labour market dynamics in Nigeria, policymakers should invest in comprehensive data collection and monitoring systems. This would enable better tracking of employment trends, the evaluation of policy interventions, and the identification of emerging challenges. By having accurate and up-to-date data, policymakers can make informed decisions and design evidence-based policies to address unemployment effectively.
5. Given the complex nature of industrial labour force dynamics, it is crucial to foster collaboration and dialogue among various stakeholders, including government agencies, private sector entities, academic institutions, and civil society organisations. This collaboration can facilitate knowledge sharing, exchange of best practices, and the development of holistic strategies to address unemployment challenges in Nigeria.

By implementing these practical recommendations, Nigeria can work towards creating a more robust and inclusive labour market, promoting sustainable employment growth, and reducing dependency on oil.

Limitations of the Study

One of the strengths of the study was that it employed robust regression analysis; which is a robust estimation technique that is less sensitive to outliers and violations of certain assumptions compared to ordinary least squares regression. This enhances the reliability and validity of the results obtained. Also, the study examined the impact of health expenditure, government capital expenditure on economic services, industrial labour force dynamics and oil revenue. By considering these variables, the study provides

a comprehensive analysis of factors that can influence unemployment levels in Nigeria. Moreover, the study utilised time series data, which allows for the analysis of trends and patterns over a specific period. This enables a better understanding of the dynamics and changes in the variables of interest, providing valuable insights into the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

However, the study focused on the Nigerian context, and the findings may not be directly applicable to other countries or regions. Economic, social, and political factors specific to Nigeria may influence the relationship between the variables studied and unemployment dynamics, and caution should be exercised when extrapolating the results to other contexts. It is important to consider these strengths and limitations when interpreting the findings of the study and when using them as a basis for decision-making and policy formulation.

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